

TECHNICAL - TACTICAL METHODS IN MODERN VOLLEYBALL GAME AND PRINCIPAL CHANGES IN VOLLEYBALL GAME

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Abstract: Volleyball is a fast-paced and strategically challenging team game in which the successful execution of technical and tactical elements is important. In the article, the author studied the technical and tactical methods of the modern volleyball game and the fundamental changes in the volleyball game.

Key words: Volleyball, sport, technical-tactical methods, rules of the game, competition, health, game, "tie-break", sports competitions.

INTRODUCTION

Along with the development of physical education and mass sports, special attention is paid to the development of major sports in our country. The fact that prestigious international and world competitions are held in our republic every year increases the interest of young people in sports. Our athletes are participating in the Asian, World and Olympic Games, achieving high results and glorifying the glory of our country.

Volleyball is included in the curriculum of all educational institutions as a subject and a source of health. Especially in recent years, volleyball has been included in the program of multi-stage and regularly held prestigious sports events such as "Umid Nihollar", "Barkamol Avlod", "Universiade", "Women's Spartakiad", "Competitions of Veterans". created the ground for a sharp increase in its geographical boundaries and the number of practitioners.

Modern volleyball has acquired a new meaning due to its natural development and drastic changes in the rules of the competition since the end of the 20th century

and the beginning of the 21st century. A fundamental change in the rules of the game is determined not only by the competition of the teams claiming to be absent, but also to some extent depends on market relations.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Volleyball is a fast-paced and strategically challenging team game in which the successful execution of technical and tactical elements is essential. Developing the skills of handling the ball and coordination of movements, as well as understanding the tactical aspects of the game, allows the team to achieve high sports results.

It is known that when conducting major prestigious competitions (World, Asian Championships, Olympic and Asian Games and other high-rated international tournaments, Cup competitions), many broadcasters and journalists have special accreditation requirements for telecasting and reporting on these competitions. they must satisfy.

If in recorded competitions the intensity of the game is low, points are often scored due to "powerful" shots, the continuous process is often interrupted and there are many stoppages, the interest in the competition is low. begins, the accreditation market becomes limited, the audience begins to narrow. Such situations continued until 1996-1998. Because, according to the old rules, "strong" attackers located in the defensive zones "earned points" as a result of jumping violently and hitting from the 4th or 2nd zones without pressing the offensive and lateral lines. The game is stopped if the ball hits the legs and waist. If the ball falls far from the field, the time is over, it is forbidden to play with another ball; if the throw-in was "lost", the opposing team was not awarded a point, if the throw-in hit the net, the game was stopped, etc. Such situations caused the game to stop frequently.

Thanks to many principled changes in today's volleyball rules, such "stopping" situations have been eliminated. In particular, the game was played with 3 balls (one ball in play, 2 balls in reserve). From the intersection of the side line and the

offensive line to the outside of the field, a 1.75 m section was limited by lines. It is allowed to play the ball with any part of the body. It was introduced that the game will be played in the "tie-break" style, that is, points will be given to the opposing team even when the ball is "lost". The "strength" of the "first" ball receiving or passing rule has been drastically relaxed, and the thrown ball will be considered "correct" if it touches the net.

Such a change in the rules of the competition sharply increased the intensity of the game, increased the activity of the players, and increased the interest of the spectators. Separately, it is worth noting that the radical change of the rules of the competition enriched the content of the game, and became the basis for the emergence of completely new generations of game methods.

In particular, shooting from defensive zones focused on the need to master the quality of diagonal jumps, the establishment of the "libero" game strengthened the defense, running and jumping the ball increased the offensive speed, etc. The new elements of the game, special qualities, methods of movement that have emerged as a result of these changes determine the importance of a new approach to the content of training sessions, including new exercises and ensuring unity of training and competition. This necessity is based on official data received in recent years. For example, Yu.D., who is known for his many fundamental scientific studies in the theory and practice of world volleyball. Zheleznyak, T.Ya. Shinulin and O.E. According to the results of Serdyukov's scientific observations, modern volleyball is increasingly changing in terms of game content due to new technical methods, tactical features and technical-tactical directions that are fundamentally different from "old" volleyball. The widespread introduction of the method of running and jumping the ball with a large "explosive-inertial force" sharply limited the possibility of receiving the ball effectively. This made the opposing team less effective in making targeted attacks.

The almost non-application of the rule to the methods of receiving and passing

the first "ball" is popularizing the methods of receiving and passing the ball with two hands from above with moderate intensity.

The widespread introduction of offensive strikes from defensive zones significantly reduced the number of combination attacks from zone 3. If until 1998, the number of attacks from the 3rd zone did not exceed 30%, in recent years the number of such attacks has decreased to 23%.

On the contrary, in the 80s, offensive strikes from defensive zones did not exceed 9.6-10%. In modern volleyball, offensive shots from the back zones have increased to 20-21%. It is self-evident that it is difficult to eliminate kicks from defensive zones with a "barrier". So, it is observed that the effectiveness of attack in volleyball today exceeds the potential of defense.

CONCLUSION

Game efficiency in today's volleyball depends on the performance skills of players with different game specializations. In particular, an attacker moving with the second pace, an attacker moving with the first pace, a passer (connector), a libero (defender).

The analysis of the matches of the world's strongest national teams allows to divide the technical and tactical actions (TTH) into two main groups in terms of the intensity of the game. The first group, represented by the high intensity of the game, includes the skills of running and jumping, attacking, blocking and playing in defense 79. The second group, represented by the average intensity of the game, included reception of the ball, guarding and various movements.

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